

Open Infrastructure Checklist for Research Performing and Research Funding Organisations

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COARA WORKING GROUP – TOWARDS OPEN
INFRASTRUCTURES FOR RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH ASSESSMENT
(OI4RRA)

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List of Acronyms

CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
OIs	Open Infrastructure
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
OS	Open Science
OI4RRA	Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment, CoARA Working Group "Towards Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment"
RRA	Responsible Research Assessment
WG	Working Group

Executive Summary

This checklist has been developed within the CoARA Working Group “Towards Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment (OI4RRA)”, as a practical extension of the group’s foundational output [Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment: Principles and Framework](#). It translates the principles, and characteristics defined in that framework into an actionable tool that supports Research Organisations—including both Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) and Research Funding Organisations (RFOs), in selecting and evaluating Open Infrastructures (OIs) aligned with Responsible Research Assessment (RRA).

The Framework established four core pillars that define an Open Infrastructure fit for RRA: **Technical Robustness, Operational Capacity, Community-driven Practices, and Ethical & Inclusive Foundations**. These categories capture the essential capabilities required for infrastructures to support transparent, equitable, auditable, and future-ready assessment workflows. They reflect the need for systems that can handle diverse research outputs, integrate qualitative and quantitative evidence, ensure traceability, uphold FAIR data principles, promote equity, and operate under community governance.

This checklist distills those pillars into a clear, practical guide that decision-makers can apply directly when assessing whether a system qualifies as an OI4RRA. It builds on the ethical, technical, and operational expectations detailed throughout the [Principles and Framework](#) output.

Designed for research managers, funding officers, librarians, IT personnel, and other decision-makers, the checklist helps organisations:

- Evaluate whether a candidate infrastructure is transparent, auditable, and community-governed
- Ensure alignment with RRA and Open Science practices
- Identify risks such as black-box algorithms, vendor lock-in, or inadequate data governance
- Compare multiple infrastructures through a consistent, principles-based lens
- Support transitions away from proprietary systems toward trustworthy, open, and community-owned alternatives

Grounding each criterion in the OI4RRA Framework, this checklist offers a coherent bridge from principles to adoption. It enables organisations to operationalize the vision articulated in the Framework, that RRA cannot be achieved on closed, opaque, or commercially controlled platforms, but requires infrastructures that are transparent, interoperable, ethically designed, community-governed, and globally inclusive.

Importantly, the checklist has undergone community validation during the Open Science Fair 2025 workshop [“Collaborative Pathways to Responsible Research Assessment via Open Infrastructures: From Principles to Practice.”](#) Feedback from practitioners, research

managers, and funders contributed to refining the clarity, scope, and practical applicability of the tool.

This tool is intended to accelerate the transition to OI4RRA by providing a simple yet rigorous mechanism for aligning organisational choices with CoARA's vision for fair, contextualized, and sustainable research assessment.

CHECKLIST FOR OPEN INFRASTRUCTURES FOR RPOs AND RFOs

Open Infrastructure Checklist for Research Organisations (including RPOs and RFOs)

A practical guide for research managers, funding officers, library and IT personnel to evaluate and select Open Infrastructures and services that align with Responsible Research Assessment, Open Science practices, and organisational priorities.

Strong & Reliable Technology

1

- High-quality Data** – Regularly updated, verified, and inclusive across disciplines.
- Transparent & Open** – Assessment methods, indicators, and workflows are documented, auditable, and reproducible.
- Interoperable** – Supports PIDs (ORCID, DOI, ROR), open APIs, and metadata standards to integrate with research systems.
- Scalable & Adaptable** – Handles large datasets, integrates new policies and evolving research needs.
- No Black-box AI** – AI-driven assessments are explainable, auditable, and free from bias.
- Secure by Design** – Includes robust cybersecurity safeguards to protect institutional systems and research data.
- Decision Traceability** – Supports end-to-end, tamper-proof audit trails that document actions, evaluations, and decisions across research management, assessment, or funding workflows (*critical for RFOs; applicable for RPOs as needed*).

Aligned with Institutional Research Policies

2

- Clear & Open Workflows** – Structured, transparent, and easy to audit.
- Recognizes all Research Contributions** – Supports datasets, software, policy impact, community engagement, and mentoring.
- Customizable** – Aligns with institutional policies and research priorities.
Reduces Workload – Uses automation to streamline data collection and reporting.
- Support & Training** – Provides helpdesks, documentation, and capacity-building resources.

Governance & Institutional Control

3

- Community-owned & Non-profit** – Managed by universities, research institutions, or academic consortia, not private corporations.
- Stakeholder Involvement** – Institutions, researchers, and funders have a clear role in governance.
- Equitable & Inclusive** – Accessible across languages, disciplines, and underrepresented research communities.
- Sustainable Funding** – Funded through public or consortial sources, avoiding reliance on commercial interests.
- Transparent Decision-making** – Clear policies and governance structures with oversight mechanisms in place.

Ethical & Responsible Research Assessment

4

- Fair & Transparent Metrics** - Avoids journal impact factor as the sole indicator, aligns with responsible research assessment principles.
- Secure & Compliant** - Meets privacy laws (e.g., GDPR) and institutional data policies.
- No Bias** - Prevents disciplinary, institutional, geographic, or gender bias in evaluations.
- Accountability & Oversight** - Includes review processes, appeal mechanisms, and governance oversight.
- Conflict-of-Interest Integrity** - Provides structured COI disclosures, transparent documentation of COI handling, and safeguards to ensure fair reviewer, panel, or committee assignment across assessment or decision-making processes (*critical for RFOs; applicable for RPOs as needed*).

Risks to consider: When to Reconsider an Open Infrastructure

- Opaque decision-making** - No clear governance structure or transparency.
 - Unexplainable AI-driven assessments** - No clarity on how AI influences rankings or funding.
 - Corporate dependence** - Heavy reliance on commercial funding without sustainability plans.
 - Lack of interoperability** - No PIDs, open APIs, or standard research tracking.
- ▶ If any of these apply, reconsider using the infrastructure.

Quick Decision Guide

- If all criteria are met:** The infrastructure is transparent, responsible, and institution-ready.
- If any are missing:** Seek alternatives that align with institutional research priorities.

Why This Checklist Matters

This checklist ensures institutions select Open Infrastructures that are:

- Transparent & Responsible** - No hidden processes or black-box AI.
- Community-Governed** - Academic-led, not commercially controlled.
- Sustainable & Future-Proof** - Financially stable and adaptable.
- Interoperable** - Works with global research standards and systems.

Use this checklist to transform your institution with Open Science and Responsible Research Assessment!

Open Systems. Shared Success. Collective Impact. **CoARA**

Organisations affiliated to this WG

- OpenAIRE AMKE
- Leiden University (CWTS)
- Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR)
- Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (TSV)
- Ss Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje
- University of Minho
- Masaryk University
- OpenCitations
- University of Debrecen
- Trinity College Dublin
- University of Bologna
- Universities Norway
- NIFU (Nordic institute for studies of innovation, research and education)
- EIFL
- Netherlands Research Council (NWO)
- COKI (Australia) *
- National Institute of Informatics (NII, Japan) *
- Michael J. Fox Foundation (United States) *
- Technische Universiteit Delft
- West and Central African Research and Education Network (WACREN, Ghana) *
- Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (Netherlands)
- UEFISCDI (Romania)
- University of Ljubljana (Slovenia)
- Netherlands eScience Center (RSD)
- UKRN
- NASA TOPS*
- University of South-Eastern Norway
- University of Hamburg
- INRIA
- Athena Research Center
- LMU Munich
- Université Côte d'Azur
- University of Novi Sad
- University of Padua
- Lusófona University
- Petre Shotadze Tbilisi Medical Academy
- CSC - IT Center for Science
- Netherlands eScience Center (RSD)
- Library and Information Centre of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences

- Training Centre in Communication (TCC Africa)
- University of Groningen
- SPARC EUROPE
- JISC

CoARA

The Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) is a collective of organisations committed to reforming the methods and processes by which research, researchers, and research organisations are evaluated. Current research assessment methods rely heavily on publication-based metrics such as citation counts and often fail to recognise the wide array of contributions made by researchers.

Over 700 research organisations, funders, assessment authorities, professional societies, and their associations have agreed on a common direction and guiding principles to implement reform in the assessment of research, researchers, and research organisations, outlined in the [Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#) published in July 2022 which provides an outline for reform and implementation.

Find out more about CoARA at www.coara.eu.

Working Group Overview

Working Groups are key communities of practice that work to implement research assessment reform in specific thematic areas. Participating members exchange knowledge, learn from each other's experience, discuss and develop outputs to advance research assessment and support the implementation of members' commitments.

The Working Group "Towards Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment" is committed to advancing the transition from closed, proprietary research infrastructures toward open, community-governed, and interoperable systems. This shift is essential for enabling ethical, transparent, and RRA practices. The group emphasizes the importance of making research information universally accessible, transparent, and inclusive of a wide diversity of disciplines, geographic contexts, languages, and research output types. It prioritizes the development of open infrastructures that are sustainable, interoperable, community-driven, and aligned with the principles of Open Science. Central to this work is the aim to support infrastructures that foster trustworthiness, equity, and inclusivity in research assessment processes, ensuring that the infrastructures themselves are fit for responsible research evaluation across varied global contexts.